

THE ROLE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES AND METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This study aims at comparing the benefits of using modern technologies and methods instead of using traditional methods. The purpose of this paper is to evaluate the traditional methods of teaching as well as multimedia teaching and to suggest other useful teaching methods that can be attempted in imparting knowledge to the students. In fact, lessons must be included two major components sending and receiving information.

Today, our country is making rapid strides in all spheres. On the verge of developing of The Republic of Uzbekistan with quick and inevitable changes, the society needs such competent generations that have thoroughly big knowledge of foreign languages, especially English. If the youth receive foreign language instruction, they can easily solve complex problems in their life. Because being qualified in another language is essential in a globalized world, which demands from people effective communication. Therefore, nowadays, the government is doing many projects, in order to increase to spread the English language through the all grades of students. Thus, being future English language specialists, we should prepare for young generations the intensive methods of learning English based on our national peculiarities. As the study of vocabulary occupies the main central place in teaching foreign languages, we would like to

investigate how to teach English vocabulary at professional colleges through one of the effective methods, suggestopedia. It is obvious that, teaching is based on two major components: teaching and receiving information. With reference to a foreign language lesson, the project is specially organized by the teacher and independently carried out by students' complex actions, and finished with a creation of a product. At present time teaching, a foreign language focuses on aims of teaching: communicative, educational, developing and bringing up goals. Among these purposes, we can say communicative aspirations takes in main part. Other aims are used to cover the tasks in communicative aim with some typical features. Teaching foreign language is also developing swiftly and according to the demand of time it applies modern methods, pedagogical technologies, interactive methods and their multimedia, monopodia

by showing their effective results. The researchers consider that the teaching would be highly effective if the teacher start to use the recent multimedia technologies like usage of computers extensively or some modifications in the conventional mode of teaching. The use of computers may be very well practiced in the environment where the use of such technology is highly possible, but there must be some sort of innovation which can also be practiced in an environment where such use of technology is on its way to growth. We analyzed some examples in some cases, which show how to achieve the several aims with the help of new intensive methods and modern technologies such as expanding student's vocabulary basement, fixing investigated lexical and grammatical material at the lesson. There is one crucial target aims, which deals with obtaining the above mentioned.

Using modern methods, approaches and new technologies help teaching foreign language effectively and intensively. There are: interactive method, communicative method, suggestopedia method, hyponomedia method, community language learning method and etc. We analyze some important points of these methods in teaching foreign languages with the help of some examples. As we know, communication is vital aspect of teaching foreign language. Because it devotes to exchange information. Similarly, it reveals learners mental abilities during the lesson. The main points of this communicative method are teaching language in communication, analyzing language materials, teaching learners how to communicate with each other's, teaching language by correcting and discussing errors. The main idea of this method is

avoiding traditional style of teaching. Learners' communication can be seen in giving opinion, retelling, and receiving information. Another effective method is suggestopedia. Bulgarian scientist Georgiy Lozanov introduced Suggestopedia. It aimed at letting out learner's inner talents which is hidden. The language is taught by influencing the learners' state of mind. More attention is given to the learner's memory. According to the some methods, the foreign language can be taught within thirty days in ten stages. In one day by four hours of teaching, it lasts six days. He also subdivided listening into the dialogues, imitation the dialogues, making up the new dialogues and the numbers of learners should be twelve in class but not more.

Advantages of this method:

1. One of the biggest advantages is effects. In fact, this method speeds the acquirement process up by at least 6 times (up to 10 times, in many cases). Learner gain any information much faster and the achievement is deeper compared to the acquisition process taking place with other methods.
2. The amount of comprehension process students absorb during a suggestopedic development is much bigger associated to what they would obtain through other approaches. Obviously, language learners gain more, in shorter time. Teachers who use suggestopedia methods while teaching take beginner level students to the intermediate level in 72 hours.
3. Some learners think that, the acquirement process is a movement of joyous and full of fun exercises, such as language games, musical activities, dancing and role play. Despite of the fact that the students are exposed to a huge amount of

motivations, they never feel under pressure, stressed or frustrated by this. The most essential side is that, in a suggestopedic lesson, students learn as easily as they did when they were little kids.

4. According to this method teachers give rather than less homework. The classes include acquirement process during the lessons. The pupils who are using this method don't have to revise the lessons at home or to do homework.

5. The students can be able to learn their target language creatively with the help of suggestopedic techniques in a spontaneous way.

6. It's a good increase of self-confidence for the students. The whole learning experience involves the students pleasantly. They can comprehend knowledge a lot without any kind of effort with joy. They link the learning of the target language with pleasant emotions and a joyful experience.

On the other hand, we cannot imagine our life without technologies. Our daily routine, jobs are connected with them as well. So what is the essential role of innovative technology in teaching foreign language? Showing one of the advantageous technologies, we can include multimedia to create a context to teach English successfully if we speak about necessity of multimedia technology, by the way we will get rid of teaching in traditional ways.

New teaching methods and technology will support teachers to the global requirement to change traditional teaching methods with technology based teaching and learning tools and facilities. In this twenty first century the term "technology" is an important issue in many fields including education. That's why technology has been becoming the knowledge conveying high way in most highly developed countries.

At the present time technology integration has gone through innovation and transformed our societies that has totally changed the way people think, work and their daily life. Apart from this, schools and other educational institutions that are supposed to prepare learners to behave in a knowledge society. Teaching and learning with technology can make many changes in school that requires for suitable planning and teaching way. In most school technical difficulties thought to become a major problem. A source of information for learners. It is causing interruptions in teaching and learning process. Furthermore, teachers' readiness and skills in using ICT are playing essential role in the use of ICT in teaching. Teachers need sufficient ICT skills to implement the technology and to have high confident level use of it in a classroom –setting and while teaching to them.

Technology support a rationale a set of aims and vision of how education systems run if ICT is integrated into teaching and learning process. Integration of Information, Communication and Technology in education mentioned to use of computers based communication that incorporates into daily classroom instructional process. In conjunction, with preparing students for the current digital era. ICT integration in education commonly means technology based transfer information and learning process that closely relates to the utilization of learning technologies in schools. Duty the fact that learners are familiar within technology and they will learn better within technology based environment. The issue of ICT integration in schools specifically in the school is vitally important.

Besides that, the use of technology in education supports a lot in the pedagogical aspects in which the application of ICT will lead to productive learning with the help of technological tools to assist. From the last statistical information shows that teaching time are not enough for teachers to use the ICT for teaching and learning purposes. It means there is no unhurried times helps for teachers so that teachers can at least use ICT for effective teaching and learning process. It is good if teachers are given more time to teach so that ICT integration in teaching can be a success. Most teachers agreed that all ICT tools provided. Teachers lack of knowledge and skills in using it. Sometimes, ICT facilities are completely provided but little access to ICT prevents teachers from using it in teaching language. Some teachers feels the urge and

motivated to use ICT in teaching but there is lack of fortifying from the school top management that delay and discourage them from using ICT. The school top management must provide an encouragement for teachers to use ICT in teaching and persuade them that ICT can benefits both teaching and learning process. As a conclusion, we know that beneficial features of using modern methods and technologies in teaching English language. We should eliminate the challenges while teaching language so as not to limit the access of utilizing modern technologies and it is clear that this century is the time of technology. In order to avoid some problems during using innovations, teachers should organize the lesson by using video materials which give a chance to keep motivation during listening exercises.

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